

POPULATION AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM NIGERIA

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Abstract: The study focuses on population on economic development in Nigeria. The data were analysed using ordinary least square (OLS) and econometrics of unit root, cointegration and error correction model. The finding revealed that the influence of population and fertility have negative and positive in short and long run, and also not having significant relationship with economic development while the mortality has negative relationship in short and long run and insignificant. Based on the findings, the study concludes that population growth has significant positive and significant impact on economic development in Nigeria. the study recommends that Nigeria government should control its rapidly growing population by formulating and implementing population and economic policies that are supportive of societal welfare; also, ensure that it reduces mortality rate by taking healthcare system in the country seriously, noting that only a healthy labour force can contribute meaningfully towards output expansion.

Keywords: Population, Economic Development, Evidence, Human development index, Nigeria

Introduction

The drive of economic development is the main focus of every developing nation. The Nigeria economic development has been in a wood were all indices have been on dwindling spiral. The is evidenced in the very low life expectancy, negligible economic growth, high morality rate, and so on. Economic development is the development of economic wealth of countries or regions for the well-being of their inhabitants (Todaro & Smith, 2006). On the other hand, population is a critical factor in the development plans of any civilized society. For effective planning for the development of developing countries such as Nigeria, it is necessary to have an actual count of the population. This will enable government to know how many people to whom they should distribute amenities and social services (Okafor, 2018). However, the relationship between population and economic development has a long history in economics. With the publishing of the ground-breaking paper titled “An essay on the principle of population” by Thomas Malthus of the classical school of thought in 1798 followed by numerous other publications by notable economics scholars including Pigou, Marshal and Keynes, the entire world became more aware of the need to understand the dynamics of population as a prerequisite to efficient economic planning as well as achieving sustainable economic growth and development (Aidi, Emecheta, &

Ngwudiobu, 2016). Empirically, Nwosu, Dike and Okwara (2014) studied the relationship between population growth and economic growth in Nigeria established that a sustainable long-run relationship between economic growth and population growth. Also, the finding of Amadi (2015) revealed that population can be managed or controlled to ensure continuous and sustainable economic growth and development in Nigeria. In furtherance, Aidi, Emecheta and Ngwudiobu (2016) revealed among other that fertility, mortality and net-migration as the proxies of population growth are significantly and inversely related to economic growth. In addition, Efuntade and Efuntade (2020) found that mortality rate has a significant negative effect on economic growth in Nigeria's perspective, while fertility rate and international migration have a significant positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria. Drawing from the foregoing, this study aims to determine the impact of population growth on economic development in Nigeria.

Literature Review

The theories concepts, and studies used in this study are discussed as follows:

Malthusian Theory

Thomas Malthus was an English clergyman who lived from 1766-1834. He was widely known as the first professional demographer. It was during the period of the physiocrat thinking in the 18th century that he postulated his theory. Malthus revolted against the prevailing optimism shared by his father and Godwin that a perfect state could be attained if human restraints could be removed. His objection was that the pressure of increasing population on the food supply would destroy perfection and there would be misery in the world. The Malthusian theory explains the relationship between the growth in food supply and in population. It states that population increases faster than food supply and if unchecked leads to vice or misery. The Malthusian doctrine is stated as follows: There is a natural sex instinct in human beings to increase at a fast rate. As a result, population increases in geometrical progression and if unchecked double itself every 25 years. Thus, starting from 1 population in successive periods of 25 years will be 1, 2, 4, 8, 16, 32, 64, 128, 256 (after 200 years). Malthus theory of population growth can be broken into eight major points based on evolution, these include: Population level is severely limited by subsistence, when the means of subsistence increases, population increases, population pressures stimulate increase in productivity, and increase in productivity stimulates further population growth. Malthus points specifically to misery, vice, and poverty. The pessimism about the economic impacts of the population on growth. He sees population trap, that is, anticipating a threshold population level at which population increase was bound to stop because life-sustaining resources, which increase at an arithmetic rate, would be insufficient to support the human population; therefore, increasing at a geometric rate.

Endogenous Growth Theory

The Endogenous Growth theory argues that economic growth is generated by forces within a system rather than external forces. It specifically argues that economic growth is a result of policies, internal processes and investment in human capital. Economic growth of a country therefore on the basis of endogenous growth is on account of government policies promoting innovation, investment in human capital and acquisition of knowledge which constitutes internal technology driving economic growth. In the context of the present study therefore,

Nigeria government policies on population growth controlling population growth through birth rates and death rates, will affect achievement of significant levels of economic growth of Nigeria. Hence, the endogenous growth theory is appropriate as the framework of the present study (Romer, 1994).

Population Growth

Population is the total number of people living within a geographical area or country at a particular time. Anyanwuocha (2006), describes population growth as the increase in the number of people that reside within a geographical or political boundary within a given period. Similarly, Ukpolo (2002) defines population as a rise in the number of people that feature in a state, country, or city. To indicate if there is a progress in population growth, there is a standard formula that is used for that for instance $(\text{birth rate} + \text{immigration}) - (\text{death rate} + \text{emigration})$. The formula used to determine whether there has been population growth is $(\text{birth rate} + \text{immigration}) - (\text{death rate} + \text{emigration})$. For this study, it is the net change in the number of persons residing in Nigeria, as following decades of very fast population growth, there is the concern that Nigeria's population growth is out-of-control, and an end seems not to be in sight. This will put pressure on available resources thereby creating gaps that will result in adverse consequences upon the nation. The measure of this in this study is Nigeria's population growth rate. Population growth is the increase in the number of individuals in a population. Global human population growth amounts to around 83 million annually, or 1.1% per year. The global population has grown from 1 billion in 1800 to 7.616 billion in 2018. It is expected to keep growing, and estimates have put the total population at 8.6 billion by mid-2030, 9.8 billion by mid-2050 and 11.2 billion by 2100. Many nations with rapid population growth have low standards of living, whereas many nations with low rates of population growth have high standards of living. Population growth is the summary parameter of trends in population abundance (Macunovich, 2000).

Economic Development

Economic development describes the underlying determinants of growth such as technological and structural changes (Ochinyabo 2021). Todaro and Smith (2006) define economic development as an increase in living standards, improvement in self-esteem, needs and freedom from oppression as well as a greater choice. Economic development also implies an increase in the per capita income of every citizen. Economic development is the development of economic wealth of countries or regions for the well-being of their inhabitants. From a policy perspective, economic development can be defined vices as efforts that seek to improve the economic well-being and quality of life for a community by creating jobs and supporting or growing incomes and the tax base. Economic development implies improvements in a variety of indicators such as literacy rates, life expectancy, and poverty rates. Economic development encompasses policies that governments undertake to meet broad economic objectives such as price stability, high employment, expanded tax base, and sustainable growth.

Human Development Index (HDI)

Human Development Index (HDI) is a statistic composite index of life expectancy, education (mean years of schooling completed and expected years of schooling upon entering the education system), and per capita income indicators, which are used to rank countries into four tiers of human development. A country scores a higher

Human Development Index when the lifespan is higher, the education level is higher, and the gross national income GNI (PPP) per capita is higher. It was developed by Pakistani economist Mahbub ul Haq and was further used to measure a country's development by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP)'s Human Development Report Office (Stanton, 2007). The human development index is a summary measure of average achievement in key dimensions of human development: a long and healthy life, being knowledgeable and have a decent standard of living. The index is the geometric mean of normalized indices for each of the three dimensions. The health dimension is assessed by life expectancy at birth, the education dimension is measured by mean of years of schooling for adults aged 25 years and more and expected years of schooling for children of school entering age. The standard of living dimension is measured by gross national income per capita (World Bank, 2018). Human Development Index is one of the best tools to keep track of the level of development of a country, as it combines all major social and economic indicators that are responsible for economic development. Since its launch in 1990, the human development index (HDI) has been an important marker of attempts to broaden measures of progress.

Empirical Studies

Ochinyabo (2021) examined rapid population growth and economic development issues in Nigeria. The was on the premier that Nigeria has a rapidly growing population forecasted to be about 400 million in 2050, with a very high proportion of youths. The country has struggled against demographic tide since independence, and there are widening gaps in poverty, unemployment, and inequality which are factors elevating the country's underdevelopment. The study adopted an ex-post facto research design and, obtained secondary data from the publications of the Central Bank of Nigeria, the National Bureau of Statistics, and the World Bank. Descriptive and Analytical statistics tools to analysed the data. The findings of the study revealed that population, remittances, gross domestic product, and unemployment negatively and significantly affect the Human Development Index in Nigeria, while foreign direct investment and effective governance exerted a positive and significant effect.

Efuntade and Efuntade (2020) carried out a study that explored the effect of population growth on the economic growth of Nigeria over the period of 1994 to 2019. Time Series data on gross domestic product (GDP), mortality rate, fertility rate, and immigration rate, were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and world development indicators. This study utilized the co-integration and vector error correction model to analyse the data. The findings of the study revealed that mortality rate has a negative significant effect on GDP in Nigeria's perceptive, while it can be concluded that fertility rate has a significant positive effect on GDP. International migration (IM) has a positive effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Onyema (2020) studied the influence of the rising population on Poverty and Unemployment in Nigeria using Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bounds (ARDL) approach on annual data from 1980-2018. The study explored the dynamic relationship between population growth and selected macroeconomic variables of economic growth, poverty, and unemployment as well as the direction of causality between them. The study also found that population growth and its components exerted a negative impact on the overall economic conditions in Nigeria.

Lawanson (2016) examined the impact of rapid population growth on economic development in Nigeria. Using the ordinary least square technique, the study showed that a growing economy such as Nigeria needs a growing population, that is, an increased supply of workers and consumers, though the exact nature of this relationship is complicated; population shows a positive but insignificant effect on economic growth (at first difference) and a negative but significant effect on economic growth (at first difference lagged) in Nigeria.

Eli, Mohammed, and Amade (2015) evaluated the impact of population growth on economic growth in Nigeria (1980-2010). The research is conducted using secondary data. Data were obtained from the World Development Indicators from 1980-2010. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics as well as regression analysis. The result revealed that there is a positive relationship between economic growth (proxied by GDP growth) and population, fertility and export growth; while negative relationships were found between economic growth (proxied by GDP growth) and life expectancy, and crude death rate.

Shah, Sargani, Ali, and Siraj (2015) examined the effect of increase in population on the economic growth of Bangladesh. The study adopted the multiple linear regression model, and the result of the study confirmed that population growth has a significant negative relationship as far as economic is concerned in Bangladesh. Two different equations were deployed; one to test the relationship between GDP growth and population the other equation used was GNI per-capita as a function of population. Both the models found that the relationship between economic growth and GNI per capita with population were suggestively different from zero. It was concluded from the literature that large size of population that is still rapidly growing will increase the consumption levels of the population as well as expenditure. When there is lesser money left for saving, it leads to a fall in investments and capital formation, and resources mobilized for economic growth will be eaten away by the fast-growing population. It is found that increase in population makes it difficult to absorb the high number of people entering into the labour market every year. In Bangladesh about 70% of those employed in the labour market are expatriate workers working in The Middle East and oil rich countries, if the population increases at higher rate it will be a problem for the government, so large increase in population will be more of a liability than an asset in a developing country like Bangladesh.

Stephan and David (2007) examined the link between population and per capita economic growth, and poverty, using the interesting case study of Uganda. Although Uganda has recently experienced excellent economic growth and poverty reduction, it currently has one of the highest population growth rates in the world which, due to the inherent demographic momentum, will persist for some time to come. By combining both a macro and micro econometric approach, using panel data, we are able to consider the impact of population growth on per capita economic growth and poverty. We find both theoretical considerations and strong empirical evidence suggest that the currently high population growth puts a considerable break on per capita growth prospects in Uganda. Moreover, it contributes significantly to low achievement in poverty reduction and is associated with households being persistently poor and moving into poverty. This is therefore likely to make substantial improvements in poverty reduction, and per capita growth, very difficult.

Methodology

Research design used is ex post facto quasi-experimental design that seeks to investigate causal relationship between the dependent and independent variables of the study, making use of already existing data which cannot be controlled or manipulated. The study used secondary (time series) data. These data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) statistical bulletin and World Bank Indicators for the period 1990 to 2021 covering a period of thirty-two years.

Model Specification

This model is specified as follows:

$$HDI = f(PGR, FTR, MTR) \quad (1.0)$$

More explicitly, the model above can be econometrically stated as:

$$HDI = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 PGR + \alpha_2 FTR + \alpha_3 MTR + \epsilon_t \quad (1.1)$$

The above model is transformed into log linear form by taking the natural log of the variables as follows:

$$\ln HDI = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln PGR + \alpha_2 \ln FTR + \alpha_3 \ln MTR + \epsilon_t \quad (1.2)$$

Where; f = functional relationship, \ln = natural logarithm, HDI = human development index, PGR = population growth rate, FTR = fertility rate, MTR = mortality rate, β_0 = Regression constant, α_1 , α_2 , and α_3 = elasticities or coefficients of population growth rate, fertility rate and mortality rate, μ_t = Stochastic or error term which captures the effect of variables that are not included in the model. The A Priori sign expectation is given as:

$$\alpha_1 > 0, \alpha_2 > 0, \text{ and } \alpha_3 > 0.$$

The analyses include multiple regression, unit root, cointegration, error correction model and so on.

Table 1.0 Multiple Regression Result

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.564282	0.098828	5.709715	0.0000
PGR	-0.099361	0.026711	-3.719895	0.0009
FTR	0.041858	0.015829	2.644387	0.0131
MTR	-2.00E-05	3.65E-05	-0.546769	0.5887
R-squared	0.870420	Mean dependent var	0.490939	
Adjusted R-squared	0.857015	S.D. dependent var	0.036253	
S.E. of regression	0.013708	Akaike info criterion	-5.628417	
Sum squared resid	0.005450	Schwarz criterion	-5.447022	
Log likelihood	96.86888	Hannan-Quinn criter.	-5.567383	
F-statistic	64.93318	Durbin-Watson stat	0.483877	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

Source: Authors' Computation (2023).

The coefficient of population growth rate (-0.099361) and a p-value (0.0000) indicates that there is a negative and significant relationship between population growth rate and human development index. This means that human development index will decrease by 9.9% given a percentage increase in population growth rate while human development index will increase by 9.9% given a percentage decrease in population growth rate. Also, the coefficient of fertility rate (0.041858) and a p-value (0.0131) indicates that there is a positive and significant relationship between fertility rate and human development index. This means that human development index will increase by 4.2% given a percentage increase in fertility rate while human development index will decrease by 4.2% given a percentage decrease in fertility rate. Lastly, the coefficient of mortality rate (-2.00E-05) and a p-value (0.5887) indicates that there is a negative and non-significant relationship between mortality rate and human development index. This means that human development index will decrease by 0.002% given a percentage increase in mortality rate while human development index will increase by 0.002% given a percentage decrease in mortality rate. From the estimated regression results, the R-squared obtained from the estimated equation is 0.870420. The R-squared value (0.870420) which is greater than 0.5(50%) shows that the regression line has goodness of fit (highly fitted). This value of R-squared also shows that about eighty-seven percent (87%) of variation in Human development index is explained by variations in population growth rate, fertility rate and mortality rate. It also means that the remaining thirteen percent (13%) of the variation in the model is captured by the error term. Also, adjusted R-squared obtained from the empirical results of the regression analysis is 0.857015. This shows that if the coefficient of determination is adjusted, approximately eight-five percent (86%) of the changes in human development index are attributable to changes in population growth rate, fertility rate and mortality rate while the remaining fourteen percent (14%) of the variation in the model is equally captured by the error term (unknown factors outside the model).

Table 1.1 Unit Root Test Result

Variable	PP	1% critical Value	5% critical Value	10% critical Value	Prob.*	Order of Integration
HDI	- 3.780339	- 3.670170	- 2.963972	- 2.621007	0.0057	1(1)
PGR	- 3.765231	- 3.670170	- 2.963972	- 2.621007	0.0079	1(1)
FTR	- 5.280201	- 3.670170	- 2.963972	- 2.621007	0.0002	1(1)
MTR	- 4.613393	- 3.689194	- 2.971853	- 2.625121	0.0010	1(1)

Source: Authors' Computation (2023).

After comparing the test statistic value against the Mackinnon critical value at 5% level of significance, it was observationally discovered that all the variables; that is, human development index (HDI), population growth rate (PGR), fertility rate (FTR) and mortality rate (MTR) in the test employed (that is, Phillips–Perron) were stationary at first difference and are all significance at 1%, 5% and 10%. This implies that human development index (HDI), population growth rate (PGR), fertility rate (FTR) and mortality rate (MTR) attain stability by first differencing. It further shows that the null hypothesis of presence of unit root was rejected after first differencing for these four variables.

Table 1.2 Johansen Cointegration Test Result

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace			Maximum Eigen Value		
		Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Values	Prob.**	Max Eigen Statistics	0.05 Critical Values	Prob.**
None *	0.652653	80.34642	69.81889	0.0057	37.72293	33.87687	0.0084
At most 1*	0.589876	48.62349	47.85613	0.0423	28.73889	27.58434	0.0238
At most 2	0.383063	21.88460	29.79707	0.3049	14.48967	21.13162	0.3262
At most 3	0.144351	7.394932	15.49471	0.5322	4.676855	14.26460	0.7819

Source: Authors’ Computation 2023

As shown in Table 1.2, since the Trace statistic value is greater than the 0.05 critical value and the Max Eigen statistic value is also greater than the 0.05 critical value at two co-integrating equations from each statistic respectively, there is therefore sufficient statistical evidence to reject the null hypothesis of no cointegration among the variables and conclude that there is existence of cointegration among all the variables at 5% level of significance. This further indicates that there exists a long run relationship or cointegration between population growth and the economic development in Nigeria. Specifically, there is long-run relationship among human development index (HDI), population growth rate (PGR), fertility rate (FTR) and mortality rate (MTR).

Table 1.3 Lag Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-1183.865	NA	1.81e+28	79.25769	79.49123	79.33240
1	-1052.555	210.0967*	1.56e+25*	*	73.57153*	72.61859*
2	-1029.534	29.16024	2.07e+25	72.30225	74.87111	73.12405

Source: Authors’ Computation (2023).

From the lag selection criteria result in Table 1.3, it can be seen that most of the criteria selected a lag of one as the optimal lag length. Based on this, all subsequent analysis will be carried out using the optimal lag length of one.

Table 1.4 Result of Error Correction Model

Dependent Variable: D(HDI)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-4.380849	98.74893	-0.044364	0.9651
D(HDI(-1))	0.583523	0.191640	3.044891	0.0067
D(PGR)	0.206083	0.091469	2.253027	0.0326
D(PGR(-1))	2.240566	4.301528	0.520877	0.6085
D(FTR)	0.319500	0.134171	2.381284	0.0246
D(FTR(-1))	0.005829	0.056398	0.103346	0.9188
D(MTR)	-0.272644	0.091622	-2.975762	0.0061
D(MTR(-1))	-0.027828	0.242770	-0.114625	0.9099
ECM(-1)	-0.292842	0.111683	-2.622073	0.0168

$R^2 = 0.756395$, $Adj R^2 = 0.670287$, $Prob(F\text{-statistic}) = 0.000040$, Durbin-Watson stat = 2.268662

Source: Authors' Computation 2023

The coefficient of population growth rate (0.206083) indicates that there is a positive relationship between population growth rate and human development index. This means that human development index will increase by 20.6% given a percentage increase in population growth rate while human development index will decrease by 20.6% given a percentage decrease in population growth rate. Also, the coefficient of fertility rate (0.319500) indicates that there is a positive relationship between fertility rate and human development index. This means that human development index will increase by 32% given a percentage increase in fertility rate while human development index will decrease by 32% given a percentage decrease in fertility. Thus, the coefficient of mortality rate (-0.272644) indicates that there is a negative relationship between mortality rate and human development index. This means that human development index will decrease by 27.3% given a percentage increase in mortality rate while human development index will increase by 27.3% given a percentage decrease in mortality rate. From the estimated regression results, the R-squared obtained from the estimated equation is 0.756395. The R-squared value (0.756395) which is greater than 0.5(50%) shows that the regression line has goodness of fit (highly fitted). This value of R-squared also shows that about seventy-six percent (76%) of variation in Human development index is explained by variations in population growth rate, fertility rate and mortality rate. It also means that the remaining twenty-four percent (24%) of the variation in the model is captured by the error term. Also, adjusted R-squared obtained from the empirical results of the regression analysis is 0.670287. This shows that if the coefficient of determination is adjusted, approximately sixty-seven percent (67%) of the changes in human development index are attributable to changes in population growth rate, fertility rate and mortality rate while the

remaining thirty-three percent (33%) of the variation in the model is equally captured by the error term (unknown factors outside the model). The tests statistical significance of the individual parameter in the model at 5% level of significance. To determine this, we compare the P-value of each parameter with the alpha value of 0.05. From the ECM result, the P-value for population growth rate is 0.0326 while the alpha value is 0.05. However, since the P-value is less than the alpha value (i.e., $0.0326 < 0.05$), we therefore conclude that population growth rate is statistically significant. From the ECM result also, the P-value for fertility rate is 0.0246 while the alpha value is 0.05. However, since the P-value is less than the alpha value (i.e., $0.0246 < 0.05$), we therefore conclude that fertility rate is statistically significant. Moreover, from the ECM result, the P-value for mortality rate is 0.0061 while the alpha value is 0.05. However, since the P-value is less than the alpha value (i.e., $0.0061 < 0.05$), we therefore conclude that mortality rate is statistically significant. The tests overall significance of the model at 5% level of significance and joint significant effects of the independent variables on the dependent variable. To determine this, we compare the prob. (F-statistic value) with the alpha value of 0.05. From the regression result, prob. (F-statistic value) is 0.000040 while the alpha value is 0.05. However, since the prob(F-statistic) value is less than the alpha value (i.e., $0.000040 < 0.05$), we therefore conclude that the ECM model estimated is statistically significant. This also means that population growth rate, fertility rate and mortality rate have joint significant effects on human development index. In conclusion, the result of the ECM in Table 1.4, shows that the coefficient of the error correction term is significant and negative. In other words, the negative sign justifies its significance. This implies that the ECM will be effective to correct any deviations from the long-run equilibrium. The coefficient of the ECM at -0.292842 also indicates that the speed of adjustment to long run equilibrium is 29.3% when any past deviation will be corrected in the present period. This means that the present value of human development index adjusts rather slowly to changes in population growth rate, fertility rate and mortality rate.

Diagnostic Tests

The Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test result in Table 4.7 shows that the probability values (0.3433) is greater than 0.05 levels of significance which imply that the null hypothesis of no serial correlation cannot be rejected. Thus, this necessitates the acceptance of null hypothesis and therefore concludes that the model has no serial correlation problem. Also, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey heteroskedasticity test result in Table 4.7 shows that the probability values (0.3129) is greater than 0.05 levels of significance which imply that the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity cannot be rejected. Thus, this necessitates the acceptance of null hypothesis and therefore concludes that the model has homoscedasticity. This implies that relevant variables were not omitted. Lastly, the Ramsey RESET test result in Table 4.7 shows that the probability values (0.4099) is greater than 0.05 levels of significance which imply that the null hypothesis of correctly specified cannot be rejected. Thus, this necessitates the acceptance of null hypothesis and therefore concludes that the model is correctly specified. This implies that the functional form of the model is correct.

Figure 1.0 Normality Test

Source: Authors' Computation (2023).

The Jarque Bera (Normality) test result in Figure 4.1 shows that the probability value (0.453271) is greater than 0.05 levels of significance which imply that the null hypothesis of Normal distribution cannot be rejected. Thus, this necessitates the acceptance of null hypothesis and therefore concludes that the model is normally distributed.

Figure 1.1 [CUSUM Test](#)

Source: Authors' Computation 2023

In testing the stability of the coefficients, the cumulative sum (CUSUM) was used. As shown in Figure 1.2, the line of CUSUM was within the 5% critical bounds. This therefore ascertain the stability of the coefficients of the regressors that have an effect on economic development in Nigeria. In conclusion, diagnostic test results in Table

4.6 provided evidence that all the variables (human development index, population growth rate, fertility rate and mortality rate) in our model conform to the basic assumptions of ordinary least squares estimation.

Discussion of the Findings

The study determined the impact of population growth on economic development in Nigeria. The study proxied population growth by population growth rate and fertility rate, mortality rate while economic development was measured by human development index. The findings of the study showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between population growth rate and human development index in Nigeria, which is in line with short run results. These results are also in agreement with the finding of Shah, Sargani, Ali and Siraj (2015) which stated that population growth rate has a positive relationship with economic growth of Bangladesh. However, Onyema (2020) established a positive and not statistically relationship. Also, findings from this study showed that there is a positive and significant relationship between fertility rate and human development index in Nigeria, this is in agreement with the short run result. This result is in consonance with theoretical a priori expectation and theory. This result is also related to the finding of Ochinabo (2021) which stated that fertility rate has a positive and significant relationship with economic development in Nigeria. Although, Eli, Mohammed, and Amade (2015) negative and significant relationship of fertility and economic development in Nigeria. Furthermore, the findings from this study showed that there is a negative and significant relationship between mortality rate and human development index in Nigeria, which is in line with short run result. The finding is also related to the finding of Efuntade and Efuntade (2020) who found that mortality rate is significantly related to economic growth in Nigeria. The overall results of the long run and short run analysis showed

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study focused on the impact of population on economic development in Nigeria. Population is a critical factor in the development plans of any civilized society. The influence of population and fertility have negative and positive in short and long run, and also not significant relationship with economic development while mortality has negative in short and long run and insignificant relationship with economic development. Based on the findings, the study concludes that population growth has significant positive and significant effect on economic development in Nigeria. This portend that population has a great influence in economic development in Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study recommends that Nigeria must control its rapidly growing population by formulating and implementing population and economic policies that are supportive of societal welfare. Besides, the average population growth rate of Nigeria should be maintained since it is found to impact positively on economic development in Nigeria within the period of study. Consequently, the Nigerian government should embark on sensitisation crusades/programmes to enlighten the Nigerian populace on the need to check fertility rate. Furthermore, population growth should be controlled in a way that high dependency ratio is avoided. In other words, the pattern of population growth should be one which allows for expansion in labour supply only (i.e., labour induced population growth). Finally, the Nigerian government should spend more in ensuring healthiness and reduced mortality in the country; noting that only a healthy labour force can contribute meaningfully in enhancement growth.

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